

Awareness and Attitude towards Organ Donation among Undergraduates, Interns, Postgraduates in Government Medical College and Hospital, Chandrapur

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Abstract:

Background: This study aims to assess the level of awareness and attitude towards organ donation among undergraduate students, interns and postgraduate students in a Government medical college and Hospital, Chandrapur.

Methodology: A questionnaire-based cross-sectional study was conducted in July 2024 at a Government medical college and Hospital, Chandrapur, involving 920 undergraduate students, interns, and residents. The study aimed to examine attitudes, awareness levels, and beliefs regarding organ donation.

Results: In this cross-sectional study conducted in July 2024 at a Government medical college and Hospital, Chandrapur, 920 participants were surveyed to understand their attitudes and awareness towards organ donation. Among them, 698 (75.8%) were undergraduate students, 78 (8.47%) were residents, and 144 (15.65%) were interns, with an average age of 21±2 years. The study revealed that 79.8% of participants were willing to donate their organs, primarily motivated by a desire to help others in need. Conversely, the main reason for hesitancy towards organ donation was the fear of misuse or trafficking of organs. Interestingly, 60.4% of respondents expressed indifference regarding who receives their organs after donation. Moreover, the survey highlighted gaps in knowledge regarding organ donation laws, with only 38.9% of participants correctly aware of the Transplantation of Human Organs Act, 1994 in India. Furthermore, nearly a quarter (24.9%) of the participants felt that the current educational curriculum lacked sufficient coverage on the topic of organ donation, suggesting a need for enhanced education in this area.

Conclusions: The study revealed a strong willingness among participants to donate organs driven by altruistic motives. Concerns about organ misuse were identified as a significant barrier. However, there was limited awareness of organ donation laws, indicating a need for improved education and transparency. Addressing these issues through targeted initiatives could enhance understanding and trust in organ donation processes, potentially increasing donation rates and benefiting those in need of transplants.

Keywords: Transplant Organ donation.

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Introduction

Human cell, tissue, and organ transplantation saves lives and restores vital functions without viable alternatives. Despite its global success over 50 years, significant disparities exist between countries in access, safety, quality, and effectiveness of transplantation practices. Ethical considerations remain paramount in the field of transplantation [1]

Organ transplantation is a crucial treatment for individuals in advanced stages of life-threatening conditions, often serving as the last resort for patients with ailments like liver and heart failure. Despite the growing need for organ transplants, the supply of available organs has shown little growth in recent years. As a result, many patients perish while waiting for the vital transplants they require. The shortage of donated organs for transplantation

remains a pressing global challenge in the 21st century. [5] There is a significant disparity between the demand and supply of human organs for transplantation. As of 2021, India's organ donation rate is 0.4 per million population.

The country needs about 500,000 organs annually, but only 2-3% of this demand is met, leading to numerous deaths from organ failure each year. In 2022, India conducted 11,423 kidney transplants, 3,718 liver transplants, and 250 heart transplants. Additionally, approximately 150,000 brain deaths occur annually in India due to accidents. [7] From 2013 to 2022, the number of deceased donors in India nearly tripled. In 2022, Telangana recorded 104 donors, while Tamil Nadu led in deceased donor transplants with 555 cases. Delhi topped the charts for live donor transplants. [2]

The decision-making process regarding organ donation is influenced by a combination of cognitive and non-cognitive factors. Identifying these factors within the general population and among medical professionals is crucial for ethical and scientific reasons. This understanding can help shape targeted communication and policy interventions, ultimately fostering truly informed decision-making. [6]

This study aimed to uncover obstacles and knowledge deficiencies impacting organ availability to boost donation rates. It specifically examined university students' awareness, attitudes, and understanding of organ donation, comparing those with and without medical education backgrounds. Insights gained from this influential demographic will guide tailored strategies to effectively address organ shortages through targeted interventions and initiatives.

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted after obtaining oral informed consent from medical students, interns, and postgraduate students at Government Medical College Chandrapur. The participants were selected using a pretested semi structured online questionnaire form. The study took place in July 2024 and included a total of 920

participants: 698 undergraduate students, 144 interns, and 78 postgraduate students from various sub-specialties. This comprehensive demographic spread allowed for a diverse and representative sample of the medical student population, providing valuable insights into their perspectives on organ donation. Data collection was facilitated through an online questionnaire, which was disseminated via social media platforms to ensure broad reach and ease of access for participants. The questionnaire aimed to gather detailed information on the participants' awareness and attitudes towards organ donation. It specifically explored whether they were willing to donate their organs and identified any objections they might have towards organ donation. By utilizing an online platform, the study was able to efficiently collect a significant amount of data in a relatively short period, ensuring that the responses were timely and relevant.

In addition to gauging willingness and objections to organ donation, the study also examined the influence of religious and family beliefs on participants' attitudes towards organ donation. Understanding these cultural and familial factors is crucial for developing targeted educational programs and interventions to address misconceptions and encourage organ donation within the medical community.

By capturing a wide range of responses, the research aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of current perceptions and willingness among medical students and professionals regarding organ donation, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of increasing organ donation rates.

Statistical Analysis

Analysis of Organ Donation Awareness and Willingness among Participants: The study involving 920 participants provides a detailed insight into the awareness and attitudes towards organ donation. Here's an elaborated analysis based on the given data:

Demographic Breakdown

Figure 1: Demographic Breakdown

Among the 920 participants:

- 57.8% (532 participants) were male.
- 41.7% (384 participants) were female.

This demographic split is crucial as it helps us understand if there are significant differences in attitudes towards organ donation between genders.

The data shows a slightly higher male participation compared to female.

Awareness of the Need for Organ Donation: A significant majority of the participants recognize the importance of organ donation: 93.4% (859 participants) believe there is a great need for organ donation.

Figure 1: Awareness of the Need for Organ Donation

This high percentage indicates a strong awareness among the participants about the critical need for organ donors. Such a high level of awareness is encouraging and suggests that educational campaigns about the importance of organ donation have been effective.

Awareness of Specific Organ Transplants: Participants' awareness about different types of organ transplants varied:

- 56.1% (516 participants) were aware of cornea transplants.
- 40.6% (374 participants) were aware of kidney transplants.
- 31.2% (286 participants) were aware of liver transplants.
- 23.6% (217 participants) were aware of heart transplants.
- 19.3% (177 participants) were aware of lung transplants.

Figure 3: Awareness of Specific Organ Transplants

This data suggests that while awareness of organ donation in general is high, knowledge about specific types of organ transplants varies significantly, with corneal transplants being the most recognized and lung transplants the least.

Willingness to Donate Organs: The participants' attitudes towards actually donating their organs show a diverse range of views:

Figure 4: Willingness to Donate Organs

Pledged Donors: The 5.5% who have already pledged their organs are crucial as they represent the active commitment towards organ donation. Despite being a small percentage, their decision can inspire others to take the same step.

Potential Donors: The majority, 68.2%, are still contemplating the decision. This group represents a significant potential for increasing the number of organ donors. Targeted awareness campaigns addressing their concerns and providing more information about the donation process could help convert these considerations into commitments.

Opposition to Donation: The 19.2% who are against organ donation indicate a segment of the population that may have strong reservations or misconceptions about the process.

Understanding their concerns—whether they are cultural, religious, or based on misinformation—is essential. Efforts to address these concerns through education and engagement could potentially reduce this opposition over time.

Gender-Based Insights: Although specific attitudes towards organ donation by gender were not provided, the demographic breakdown could help tailor future campaigns. For instance:

If men are found to be more willing or reluctant to donate compared to women, gender-specific messages could be developed.

Understanding any gender-specific barriers or motivators could help in designing more effective communication strategies.

Conclusion

The data from this study underscores a high level of awareness about the need for organ donation, which is a positive sign. However, the relatively low percentage of individuals who have already pledged their organs indicates that more efforts are needed to translate awareness into action. By focusing on educating those who are still

contemplating donation and addressing the concerns of those who are opposed, it is possible to increase the number of pledged organ donors. Gender-specific insights can further enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives.

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